

Intentionally added plastics in personal care products – a key source of microplastics to the environment

Fate, effects, and mitigation strategies

Introduction

Microplastics are small pieces of plastic (longest dimension ≤ 5 mm). They are widely distributed in the environment, with evidence of harm at multiple levels of biological organisation^{1,2}. Microplastics originate from multiple sources; subdivided as primary microplastics, which are manufactured to be < 5 mm, including: preproduction pellets³ and particles that are intentionally added to products such as paints⁴, household and industrial cleaning products, and cosmetics. Secondary microplastics are generated by the wear of larger items including tyres⁵, textiles⁶ and plastic debris. It is estimated that 12.7 million tonnes of microplastics enter the environment annually⁷. They are persistent and cannot effectively be removed, hence, interventions to minimise releases are key.

This document focuses on personal care products (PCPs), which are estimated to account for an annual release of 47,000 tonnes (0.047 million tonnes)⁷ of microplastics to the environment.

Personal care products as a source

A key source of microplastics are those intentionally added to PCPs, including “rinse off” products such as cosmetics, sunscreens, antiperspirants, facial scrubs, and soaps, as well as toothpaste. The plastic particles used in these products are typically 1 - 1000 μm in size, and some products can contain millions of plastic particles that are subsequently released to waste water⁸.

Microplastics intentionally added in the manufacture of PCPs are typically called “microbeads” and exist in various shapes including ellipses, irregular fragments, and spheres^{8,9}. Some locations benefit from advanced wastewater treatment, which can capture a substantial proportion of larger microplastics (~ 300 μm). However, such facilities are lacking in many parts of the world. Any microplastics that are not captured will pass to the environment with ‘treated’ water¹⁰. In addition, it is common practice to apply biosolids from wastewater, which contain captured plastic particles, to land as fertiliser¹¹ or to incinerate them. These practices can result in emissions of microplastics and carbon dioxide^{12,13}.

“Microbeads” are typically made from polyethylene (PE) (including glitter commonly used in cosmetics), but also include poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET), nylon, polypropylene (PP) and poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA)^{8,9}. Like all plastics, once in the environment, these microplastics will weather and fragment into smaller particles¹⁴.

Microbeads can be redistributed by air, water and organisms. Their heterogeneity results in differing transport potential to that of natural particles¹⁵. While natural particles are a normal component of ecosystem dynamics and cause minimal harm, there is substantial evidence of toxicity resulting from exposure to microplastics^{16,17} including exposure to microplastics from PCPs¹⁸.

While there is limited information on the chemical composition of microplastics used in PCPs, plastics more generally contain mixtures of polymers, unreacted monomers, oligomers, additives, and non-intentionally added substances (NIAS)^{*,19}. Microplastics including those used in PCPs can also accumulate harmful chemicals⁸ such as heavy metals and organic pollutants from the environment and may facilitate their uptake by organisms. In addition, surface colonisation by microbes can result in transport of pathogens including *Vibrio spp.* and *E. coli*, and antibiotic resistance genes^{20,21}.

A survey in the UK indicated consumers were alarmed about the presence of plastic microbeads in their cosmetics, and that the societal benefit of this intentional addition of microplastics was unclear²².

Ingestion of PCPs in oral healthcare products²³ represents a key exposure pathway into the human body while dermal absorption is an emerging health concern as a potential pathway for products containing PCPs that are applied to the skin. For example, concerns are being raised about the small particle sizes of microplastics present in PCPs including sunscreens²⁴ and face-scrubs²⁵.

Figure 1. Left: Intentionally added microplastics (microbeads) extracted from a cosmetic product (60 times magnification); Top right: microbeads extracted from a range of cosmetics in 2015/8, shown in small jars in front of the product. Some of these products contain millions of these plastic particles. Bottom left: the same products had no such particles (empty jars) after UK legislation in 2018. Source: University of Plymouth

Interventions to eliminate the release of intentionally added microplastics

Regulating and monitoring primary microplastics that are manufactured (≤ 5 mm) and intentionally added to PCPs (Fig. 1) can be relatively straightforward. For example, microbeads added to PCPs have now been banned in multiple countries, as well as the European Economic Area (EEA)²⁶, and in 2023 the EU chemical legislation REACH expanded this ban to all products containing intentionally added microplastics²⁷.

The global plastics treaty provides a key opportunity to regulate the production, use in manufacturing, sale, distribution, and import or export of microplastics that are “intentionally added” to products (Articles 3 and 5; Chair’s text December 2024)²⁸.

Concerns have been raised about replacing conventional plastics in these products with biodegradable plastic “alternatives”, because it is unlikely these will readily degrade in the natural environment^{9,29}. Several natural non-plastic substitutes have been shown to outcompete plastic microbeads in terms of resource availability, environmental impact, and human health impact, including wheat grain, pumice, silica, sea salt,³⁰ and they were often cheaper than plastic options.

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Authors: Freija Mendrik, Trisia Farrelly, Stephanie Reynaud, Winnie Courtene-Jones, Richard C. Thompson

Reviewers: Justin Boucher, Bethanie Carney Almroth, Florin-Constantin Mihai, Valentin Dettling, Martin Wagner

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